

JURISPRUDENCE

PROTECTION OF CONSUMER RIGHTS IN DISTANCE SELLING CONTRACTS – URGE TO REFORM GEORGIAN PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract

The Association Agreement between Georgia and the European Union has initiated a significant process of legislative approximation, including the recent transposition of Directive 2011/83/EU on consumer rights into Georgian law. Despite this progress in substantive consumer regulation, the protection afforded to consumers in cross-border distance selling contracts remains structurally inadequate at the level of private international law. Presented article delivers interim conclusions from my ongoing PhD thesis on critical analyzes of current framework of the Law of Georgia on Private International Law (GPIL).

The article examines the EU's dual-layered system of consumer protection: a substantive layer, under Rome I, ensuring the application of the consumer's habitual residence law and restricting harmful choice-of-law clauses through a semi-mandatory regime; and a procedural layer, under Brussels Ibis, granting asymmetric jurisdictional privileges, home-forum protection, and tight control over forum-selection clauses. Employing a combination of doctrinal, comparative, teleological, and normative-analytical methods study integrates elements of case-law analysis, focusing on key decisions of the Court of Justice of the European Union the article proposes a comprehensive reform of Georgian private international law and civil procedure.

Keywords: Consumer rights, Private International Law, Substantive Protection, Procedural Protection, Distance Selling,

1. Introduction

The Association Agreement between Georgia and the EU, signed on 27 June 2014 and entered into force on 1 July 2016, gave rise to comprehensive harmonization process of legislature between European Union and Georgia.¹ The conclusion and implementation of such agreements form part of the EU's broader European Neighborhood Policy (hereinafter, the "ENP"), which aims to deepen integration with its eastern partner states, including Georgia.² Integration in sphere of protection of consumer rights was reflected in adoption of law of Georgia on the protection of consumer rights, corresponding obligation on implementation Directive 97/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 1997 on the protection of consumers in respect of distance contracts, prescribed by the Association Agreement between Georgia and the EU.³ Since, approximation of legislation took place in 2022, Parliament of Georgia surpassed minimum obligation of harmonization and transpositioned Directive 2011/83/EU

of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on consumer rights, amending among others, Directive 97/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council.⁴

In the light of latest legislative developments in the sphere of consumer rights, protection mechanisms offered in cross-border consumer transactions are still weak. Particularly, Georgian law on private international law (GPIL) although ensures mandatory protection for consumers, the protection afforded by Article 38 of GPIL remains insufficient for achieving that goal – it fails to meet attested standards of EU, including Rome I regulation⁵ and leaves consumers vulnerable in cross-border distance selling contracts.

2. Notion of Consumer under European PIL

Protective jurisdictional regime on consumer rights established by the Brussels Ibis Regulation⁶ is designed on the concept of consumer, as **jurisdictional gatekeeping device** designed to protect weaker parties

¹ Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, OJ L 261, 30.8.2014, pp. 4–743, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/agree_internation/2014/494/oj/eng, accessed <09.12.2025>

² Pieter Jan Kuijper, Jan Wouters, Frank Hoffmiester, Geert De Baere and Tomas Ramopoulos, *The Law of EU External Relations: Cases Materials and Commentaries on the EU as an international Legal Actor* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press) 556.

³ Annex XXIX to the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, OJ L 261, 30.8.2014, pp. 4–743, [https://eur-](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/agree_internation/2014/494/oj/eng)

[lex.europa.eu/eli/agree_internation/2014/494/oj/eng](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/agree_internation/2014/494/oj/eng), accessed <09.12.2025>

⁴ Directive 2011/83/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on consumer rights, amending Council Directive 93/13/EEC and Directive 1999/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Directive 85/577/EEC and Directive 97/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Text with EEA relevance, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2011/83/oj/eng>, accessed <09.12.2025>

⁵ Gogichaishvili, E. (2018) 'Comparative Analysis of Consumer Protection Under the Law of Georgia on Private International Law and the Rome I Regulation', *Georgian Law Journal*, 2(1).35-36.

⁶ European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation).Article 17-19;

in cross-border contractual disputes. The definition is restrictive, autonomous, and interpreted in light of its purpose—to protect the weaker party.⁷ **Imbalance of bargaining power** between professionals and individuals acting outside their trade, urges European Court of Justice to interpret definition of consumer strictly but purposively. As it is reflected in *Benincasa v. Dentalkit*, even if future activities of the party entering the commercial arrangement were not yet commenced, could not qualify as a consumer because protection is confined to “private final consumption.”⁸ Similarly, *CJEU* refined the notion of “mixed-purpose contracts,” stating that the consumer status applies only if the professional purpose is marginal. In other words, Gruber doctrine states that if a contract has both private and professional elements, consumer status exists only if the professional aspect is so negligible that it “plays no part at all.”⁹ Moreover, later case law confirms the principle: commercial activity even if ancillary—disqualifies consumer status.¹⁰

Key implications of Brussels Ibis Regulation on consumer implies that **only natural persons** qualify as consumers, purpose of transaction should be determined objectively and burden of proof lies with the party invoking consumer status.¹¹

With respect to distance selling contracts, requirements of internationality and cross-border element in private contracts attested in previously established case law,¹² specifies additional yardsticks to measure scope of application of Brussels I/ibis regime. Specifically, cross-border online consumer contract should satisfy three prerequisites. Firstly, trader should envisage doing business in state of that consumer’s domicile, in the sense that it was minded to conclude a contract with them. Secondly, international nature of trader’s activity should entail use of language or a currency of the state of consumer’s domicile, other than the language or currency generally used in the Member State in which the trader is established with the possibility of making and confirming the reservation in that other language, mention of telephone numbers with an international code, outlay of expenditure on an internet referencing service in order to facilitate access to the trader’s site or that of its intermediary by consumers domiciled in other Member States, use of a top-level domain name other than that of the Member State in which the trader is estab-

lished, and mention of an international clientele composed of customers domiciled in various Member States. Thirdly, mere accessibility of the trader’s or the intermediary’s website in the Member State in which the consumer is domiciled is insufficient.¹³

Moreover, contract still may be concluded offline if initial targeting was online¹⁴ and causal link between online targeting and conclusion of contract is not required, to establish conclusion of distance consumer contract.¹⁵

To conclude, Articles 17-19 of Brussels Ibis regulation and practice of CJEU, makes it evident that notion of consumer under European international private law, should be interpreted strictly, according to narrow definition of the legislation. It has autonomous meaning under EU law, including recently developed practice of CJEU. Moreover, on case-by-case bases, notion shall not be precluded from teleological interpretation and functionality of purpose of the contract under consideration.

Similarly, EU’s commitment to the weaker party doctrine is reflected in Article 6 Rome I regulation, which established special choice of law rule for consumer contracts, that structurally parallels Articles 17–19 Brussels Ibis, though it governs applicable law rather than jurisdiction.¹⁶ Article 6 applies only where one party is a consumer, meaning a natural person acting outside his trade or profession, echoing general approach of EU towards definition of the notion of consumer, which should be acknowledged as strictly functional and must be interpreted autonomously.¹⁷ Such approach, excludes from the notion legal persons, natural persons acting for business purposes, even if economically weak, individuals engaged in preparatory entrepreneurial activity.¹⁸

Scope of application of Rome I regulation is circumscribed to the consumer contracts explicitly listed in the regulation as follows: sale of goods, supply of services, consumer credit, contracts concluded with a professional who **directs activities** to the consumer’s state.¹⁹ Therefore, Article 6 must not be expended beyond its explicit text and apply to exemptions listed²⁰ in the text or otherwise.²¹

Both Rome I and Brussels Ibis adopt an autonomous concept of consumer, defined as a natural person acting for purposes outside his trade or profession.²²

⁷ Magnus U., Mankowski P., 2016. European Commentaries on Private International Law (ECPI), Brussels Ibis Regulation Commentary, 343-344.

⁸ *Benincasa v. Dentalkit* (Case C-269/95)

⁹ *Gruber v. BayWa* (Case C-464/01)

¹⁰ ECJ, *Schrems v Facebook*, Case C-498/16

¹¹ Magnus U., Mankowski P., 2016. European Commentaries on Private International Law (ECPI), Brussels Ibis Regulation Commentary, 443-454.

¹² *Hypotecni bank a.s.v. Udo Mike Lindner* (Case C-327/10), [2011] ECR I-11543 para.29; *Armin Maletic and Marianne Maletic v. lastminute.com GmbH and TUI Osterreich GmbH* (Case C-478/12), ECLI:EU:C:2013:735 para. 25;

¹³ *Pammer and Hotel Alpenhof* (Joined Cases C-585/08 and C-144/09).

¹⁴ *Mühlleitner* (C-190/11);

¹⁵ *Emrek* (C-218/12);

¹⁶ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier, p 453.

¹⁷ *Ibid*, p 458.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, pp 458–459.

¹⁹ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), article 6(1).

²⁰ Article 6(4) excludes from the scope transportation contracts, save for package tours. Contracts covering financial instruments outside retail settings and insurance contracts (covered separately) are out of scope of the Rome I Regulation.

²¹ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier, p 455.

²² Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private Interna-*

Term “consumer” is a strictly functional concept, determined by the purpose of the contract rather than the subjective status of the party,²³ derived from the normative premise that consumers are typically less informed, less powerful, and less capable of negotiating favorable contractual terms than professionals are – such protection embodies a “structural asymmetry”, justified by the imbalance of information and bargaining power.²⁴

3. Concept of Consumer under Georgian PIL

The Law of Georgia on Public International Law explicitly recognizes the importance of protecting consumer rights. Article on “Imperative rules of social protection” provides: “The choice of law shall be considered void if it disregards the imperative rules that are adopted to protect customers and employees from discrimination. This rule shall also apply to the delivery and financing of movable property, or labour or service contracts if they are agreed upon or concluded in a country in which the customers and employees have their place of residence and where these protective rules operate.”²⁵

Although first sentence of Article 38 demonstrates that parties retain autonomy to choose the applicable law, including in consumer contracts, such choice is limited by mandatory protective norms. Its main objective is to protect the consumer from discriminatory treatment—any choice of law leading to discrimination against the consumer will be null and void, and the national law will govern the contract instead. Addressing only discrimination-based violations, mechanism afforded by Article 38 remains insufficient to ensure mandatory protection for consumers, since consumer interests extend beyond the issue of discriminatory treatment.²⁶

Unlike explicit and clear definitions of notion of “consumer” provided by acts of European PIL (“person outside his trade or profession”),²⁷ the Law of Georgia on Private International Law fails to articulate a clear, coherent, and operational definition of the concept of a “consumer,” thereby creating interpretative uncertainty and limiting doctrinal consistency in the application of consumer-protective conflict-of-law rules.

The Law of Georgia on the Protection of Consumer Rights defines the consumer as “any natural person who is offered goods or services, or who purchases

or further consumes goods or services exclusively for private purposes and not for performing any commercial practice or industrial activity, crafting or other occupational activities.”²⁸ Yet, notwithstanding the presence of this sector-specific formulation, the autonomous incorporation of the consumer notion into the Law of Georgia on Private International Law remains indispensable. The GPIL operates within a distinct normative and methodological domain—namely, the allocation of legislative competence and the calibration of party autonomy in cross-border contractual settings—where the classification of a party as a consumer must be shaped by PIL-specific criteria.²⁹ These include the existence of an international element, a contract-specific and purpose-sensitive analysis of the party’s role, and the narrow, exception-based interpretative approach traditionally demanded by protective conflict-of-laws rules.³⁰ Although the CPR Law definition closely reflects the structure and language of the consumer concept developed in the Rome I and Brussels Ibis Regulations, this parallelism cannot substitute for a clearly articulated and functionally autonomous definition embedded within the GPIL itself. Only such a PIL-tailored notion can safeguard doctrinal coherence, ensure genuine harmonization with European private international law standards, and provide the degree of legal certainty and predictability required for Georgia’s evolving conflict-of-laws jurisprudence.

4. Two folded system of consumer protection

European private international law constructs consumer protection on a dual foundation: substantive protection, provided primarily by Article 6 of the Rome I Regulation, and procedural protection, enshrined in Articles 17–19 of the Brussels Ibis Regulation. These instruments operate simultaneously yet independently, each addressing distinct vulnerabilities inherent in cross-border consumer transactions. Substantive protection secures the content of consumer rights by ensuring the application of mandatory consumer law, while procedural protection guarantees a fair and accessible forum in which those rights may be enforced. The architecture is described by Briggs as a “two-lane but tightly interlocked system,”³¹ and by Tang as a “complementary equilibrium between justice in substance and justice in access.”³² The following subparagraphs analyse these two dimensions in detail, explaining how

tional Law: Rome I Regulation. Munich: Sellier 458; 11. Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (2016) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Brussels Ibis Regulation Commentary*. Munich: Sellier, p 443.

²³ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier, p 458-460.

²⁴ Basedow J., 2008, *Consumer Protection in PIL*, *European Review of Private Law (ERPL)*, Vol. 10, p. 833

²⁵ The Law of Georgia on Public International Law, Article 38. <https://matsne.gov.ge/en/document/view/93712?publication=6>, accessed <10/12/2025>

²⁶ Gabisonia Z., Kartuli Saertashoriso Kerdzo Samartali [Georgian Private International Law] (Meridiani, 2011) pp 301-302.

²⁷ Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and

commercial matters (recast), Article 17(1); Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I), Article 6(1).

²⁸ Law of Georgia On the Protection of Consumer Rights, Article 4 (i), 1455-VIII06-X03, 29/03/2022. <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/en/document/view/5420598?publication=0>

²⁹ Cachia P., 2009, *Consumer Contracts in European Private International Law*, *European Law Review*, 34(3): pp 480–481.

³⁰ Max Planck Institute (2007) ‘Comments on the Commission’s Proposal for Rome I Regulation’, *Rechts Zeitschrift für ausländisches und internationales Privatrecht*, pp 230-233.

³¹ Briggs, A. (2019) *Private International Law in English Courts*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp 710–715.

³² Tang, Z.S. (2015) *Electronic Consumer Contracts in EU Private International Law*. Oxford: Hart Publishing, pp 3–7.

they operate, the principles underlying them, and how they can reinforce reform of Georgian PIL.

4.1. Substantive Protection Under Article 6 of the Rome I Regulation

Substantive protection delivered through Article 6 Rome I, ensures that consumers—defined strictly as natural persons acting outside their trade or profession—cannot be deprived of the substantive safeguards of their habitual residence, regardless of any contractual choice-of-law clause. This is the doctrinal core of the system and reflects the EU’s recognition that consumers possess weaker bargaining power and typically lack the expertise to assess the implications of foreign governing law. Central to Article 6 is the principle that the law of the consumer’s habitual residence applies by default.³³ Habitual residence represents not only the consumer’s social and legal environment but also the jurisdiction whose norms the consumer can reasonably expect to apply. This “expectation principle” is essential to the legitimacy of consumer PIL: consumers transact within a psychological and informational bubble shaped by their domestic law.³⁴

The second pillar of substantive protection prescribed by the act is the semi-mandatory nature of party autonomy: while parties may choose an applicable law, such choice cannot deprive the consumer of the protection provided by the mandatory provisions of their habitual residence.³⁵ Academic writers have aptly described this as a “double filter” or “dual-application model”: the chosen law applies in principle, but mandatory consumer-protective rules from the habitual residence override it where necessary.³⁶ This system prevents evasion of stronger consumer standards and curtails regulatory arbitrage. Case law reinforces this model, ensuring that the regime is not exploited by traders or by individuals attempting to self-categorize strategically.³⁷

A crucial component of Article 6’s substantive protection is the directed activity requirement. Traders must direct or pursue commercial activity toward the consumer’s state, and the contract must fall within such activity, identifying factors such as multilingual websites, use of foreign currencies, or shipping policies as indicators of directed activity.³⁸ In *Emrek*, the Court clarified that no causal link is needed between the directed activity and the consumer’s decision to contract, a highly protective approach that expands substantive protection even in digitally diffuse markets.³⁹ These judgments are observed as “future-proof” consumer

law for e-commerce, where consumer behavior is often serendipitous and not easily attributable to singular advertising triggers.⁴⁰

4.2. Procedural Protection

If substantive protection ensures what rights consumers possess, procedural protection ensures where and how those rights may be enforced. Hallmark of Articles 17–19 Brussels Ibis is jurisdictional asymmetry: consumers may sue the professional either in the professional’s domicile or in their own domicile, but professionals may bring proceedings only in the consumer’s domicile.⁴¹ This asymmetry reflects the recognition that litigation abroad imposes financial, linguistic, logistical, and psychological burdens on consumers that professionals are structurally better positioned to bear. In other words, economic realities of cross-border litigation—translation costs, travel expenses, and differences in legal representation—create formidable barriers that procedural rules must counterbalance if consumer protection is to be effective.⁴²

In doctrinal terms, Brussels Ibis secures three procedural pillars: home forum privilege, forum actoris prohibition for professionals, and limited validity of jurisdiction clauses. The home forum privilege means consumers cannot be forced to litigate in a foreign forum; Article 19 provides that jurisdiction clauses in consumer contracts are valid only if concluded after the dispute has arisen or if they confer additional rights on consumers.⁴³ This approach based on the premise that consumers cannot meaningfully consent to jurisdictional disadvantage in pre-dispute contracts.⁴⁴

The interaction between Rome I and Brussels Ibis forms a unified European model of consumer PIL. Their mutual reinforcement is reflected in “integrated model of consumer justice,” wherein conflict-of-laws rules and jurisdictional rules must be interpreted together as part of a broader constitutional structure of fairness.⁴⁵

5. Reform of Georgian PIL – strengthening substantive and procedural protection of consumer rights.

In the light of provided research results, reform of Georgian PIL should commence by recognizing the architecture of the EU model. Consumer protection in EU private international law is constructed on two interlocking axes: substantive protection under Article 6 of the Rome I Regulation (benefiting from mandatory

³³ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), Art 6(1).

³⁴ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Manikowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier, p 453.

³⁵ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), Art 6(2).

³⁶ Dickinson, A. (2010) *The Rome I Regulation: The Law Applicable to Contractual Obligations in Europe*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 341–348.

³⁷ Case C-464/01 *Gruber v BayWa* [2005] ECR I-439.

³⁸ Joined Cases C-585/08 and C-144/09 *Pammer and Hotel Alpenhof* [2010] ECR I-12527.

³⁹ Case C-218/12 *Emrek v Sabranovic* [2013] ECLI:EU:C:2013:666.

⁴⁰ Tang, Z.S. (2015) *Electronic Consumer Contracts in EU Private International Law*. Oxford: Hart Publishing, 77-82

⁴¹ European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation), Art 18.

⁴² Weatherill, S. (2021) *EU Consumer Law and Policy*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp 121–128.

⁴³ European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation), Art 19.

⁴⁴ Peter Mankowski, ‘Consumer Contracts, Arts 17–19’ in *Brussels Ibis Commentary* (Sellier 2016) 444–446.

⁴⁵ Nevena Lazić and Alexander Loacker (eds), *Judicial Cooperation in Civil Matters* (Springer 2018).

rules of the law of their habitual residence)⁴⁶ and procedural protection under Articles 17–19 of the Brussels Ibis Regulation (securing home forum, thus preventing jurisdiction clauses and procedural manoeuvring from neutralising the substantive protection secured by Rome I).⁴⁷

5.1. Proposals for substantive reforms

By contrast, GPIL lacks a clear definition of “consumer”, does not anchor consumer contracts in the law of the consumer’s habitual residence, and affords broad and largely unchecked freedom of choice to traders in designing applicable-law clauses. More significantly, Georgian procedural rules do not provide an asymmetric jurisdiction regime comparable to Brussels Ibis, leaving consumers vulnerable to pre-dispute jurisdiction clauses designating foreign courts that are practically inaccessible.⁴⁸ As a result, Georgian consumers can be deprived both of the substantive protections of their own law and of realistic access to justice in their home courts.

Besides, urge for introduction of narrow definition of “consumer” in the image of Article 6 Rome I. Argued in paragraph 3 of the presented article, the conflict rule itself should be recast so that habitual residence becomes the central connecting factor. Article 6(1) Rome I designates the law of the consumer’s habitual residence as the default applicable law where a professional directs activities to that state and the contract falls within those activities.⁴⁹ Habitual residence is not chosen arbitrarily – it reflects the social and regulatory environment in which the consumer lives, forms expectations, and organises their economic life.⁵⁰ A possible example of reform wording could be along the following formulation, which tracks the structure of Article 6(1) Rome I and would provide a stable default rule in Georgian law:

“A contract concluded between a natural person acting for purposes outside their trade, business or profession (‘consumer’) and a person acting in the course of their trade, business or profession (‘professional’) shall, in the absence of a valid choice of law, be governed by the law of the country in which the consumer has their habitual residence, provided that the professional pursues or directs commercial activities to that country and the contract falls within the scope of such activities.”

⁴⁶ Ulrich Magnus, ‘Article 6 Rome I’ in Ulrich Magnus and Peter Mankowski (eds), *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation* (Sellier 2017) 453–458.

⁴⁷ Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (2016) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Brussels Ibis Regulation Commentary*. Munich: Sellier, pp 443–446.

⁴⁸ Parliament of Georgia (2009) *Law of Georgia on Public International Law*, Article 38.

⁴⁹ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), art. 6(1).

⁵⁰ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier, p. 454.

⁵¹ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), art 6(2).

However, modern consumer conflict-of-laws is not satisfied with a mere choice of connecting factor; Article 6(2) Rome I permits the parties to choose the applicable law but stipulates that this choice may not deprive the consumer of the protection afforded by mandatory provisions of the law of their habitual residence.⁵¹ Which can be described as “mandatory minimum protection rule” that prevents traders from using choice-of-law clauses to export weaker regulatory regimes to consumers,⁵² “floor” that party autonomy cannot breach.⁵³ To remedy described shortcoming in Georgian law on PIL, Article 38 should be amended to state explicitly that any choice of law in a consumer contract cannot reduce the level of protection guaranteed by the mandatory rules of the law of the consumer’s habitual residence. In statutory language, this might read:

“The parties may choose the law applicable to a consumer contract. Such choice shall not, however, have the result of depriving the consumer of the protection afforded by the mandatory provisions of the law of the country in which the consumer has their habitual residence.”

This reform would bring GPIL into close doctrinal alignment with the EU model and meaningfully restrain the use of aggressive choice-of-law clauses in standard terms.

A further indispensable component of reform is the incorporation of the directed activity requirement to address predicaments with safeguarding consumer rights in distance selling contracts. Both Rome I Article 6 and Brussels Ibis Articles 17–19 apply only where the professional “pursues or directs” activities to the state of the consumer’s domicile or habitual residence.⁵⁴ Non-exhaustive list of indicators of directed activity, such as the use of foreign-language websites, foreign currencies, explicit references to foreign customers, or delivery arrangements into other states – prescribed by CJEU case law, can be incorporated in the law on PIL,⁵⁵ to be considered holistically, with no single factor being decisive.⁵⁶

5.2. Proposals for procedural reforms

All these substantive reforms would be incomplete without corresponding procedural reforms in Georgian civil procedure. Even if Article 38 GPIL were brought into line with Article 6 Rome I, consumers would continue to face significant obstacles if jurisdiction clauses

⁵² Rühl, G. (2009) ‘Consumer Protection in Private International Law: The Limits of Party Autonomy’, *Yearbook of Private International Law*, 10, pp 120–122.

⁵³ Briggs, A. (2019) *Private International Law in English Courts*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp 710–713.

⁵⁴ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation); European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation), art 17(1).

⁵⁵ Joined Cases C-585/08 and C-144/09 *Pammer v Reederei Schlüter and Hotel Alpenhof v Heller* [2010] ECR I-12527.

⁵⁶ Magnus, U. (2017) ‘Art 6 Rome I’, in Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (eds) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Rome I Regulation*. Munich: Sellier., p. 457.

allowed traders to sue them in foreign courts. Brussels Ibis responds to this problem by granting consumers the right to sue in their own domicile and by allowing traders to sue consumers only in that domicile.⁵⁷ This asymmetry is deliberate, reflecting the structural inequality between consumers and professionals in cross-border disputes.⁵⁸ A Georgian reform that seeks genuine equivalence with EU standards should therefore amend the Civil Procedure Code to adopt an analogous rule: consumers domiciled in Georgia should have the right to bring proceedings either in their own courts or, at their election, in the courts of the trader's domicile, while foreign or domestic traders should be permitted to sue Georgian consumers only in Georgian courts. Moreover, Georgian law should follow the same path provided under Brussels Ibis Article 19; such clauses are valid only if concluded after the dispute has arisen or if they confer additional rights on the consumer.⁵⁹ Such rule will provide that pre-dispute jurisdiction clauses designating foreign courts are unenforceable against consumers unless they grant the consumer an option of additional fora. Finally, the reform package should address the role of overriding mandatory rules in Georgian law, confirming that overriding mandatory rules should be construed narrowly and primarily in regulatory fields such as labour law or commercial agency rather than consumer contracts.⁶⁰

In summary, comparative practice supports this direction of travel. Several Central and Eastern European states, including Poland and the Baltic republics, reformed their private international law statutes after accession to the EU by incorporating Rome I and Brussels Ibis concepts almost verbatim, particularly in relation to consumer contracts,⁶¹ enhancing legal certainty, supporting cross-border commerce, and improving the position of consumers without imposing disproportionate burdens on traders.⁶² Thus, such reforms would bring Georgian law into line with European standards, fulfil obligations flowing from the Association Agreement, and, most importantly, equip Georgian consumers with meaningful protection in an increasingly complex and borderless marketplace.

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⁵⁷ European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation), art 18.

⁵⁸ Magnus, U. & Mankowski, P. (2016) *European Commentaries on Private International Law: Brussels Ibis Regulation Commentary*. Munich: Sellier, pp. 444-445.

⁵⁹ European Parliament and Council (2012) Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 (Brussels Ibis Regulation), art 19.

⁶⁰ European Parliament and Council (2008) Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 (Rome I Regulation), recital 37, Case C-478/99 *Commission v Belgium (Arblade)* [2001] ECR I-8455; Case

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